

tion of nitrogen but received 30 kg N/ha at 2 and 4 weeks after emergence (WE). Others received a basal nitrogen application of 104 kg N/ha and, at 4 WE, additional nitrogen needed to make the total amount 60 kg N/ha. At 8 WE, all plots received an additional 40 kg N/ha.

All plots received a total of 100 kg N/ha. Each plot was weeded 3 times: 2, 5, and 8 WE. Before each weeding, and at harvest, weeds were sampled from three quadrats (0.5 × 0.5 m/plot), counted, and weighed.

At 2 WE, no significant difference in weed count was observed, but the weight of weeds harvested from the plots that received a basal application of 40 kg N/ha was significantly higher than that of weeds harvested from the plots that received a basal application of 0 or 10 kg N/ha (see table). Plots with smaller amounts of basal fertilizer were easier to weed because the weeds, primarily grasses, were smaller and easier to distinguish from the rice.

Topdressing of nitrogen affected the weed count 5 WE. The number of

weeds in the plots that received 20 kg N/ha as a topdressing was significantly lower than that in the plots that had received 4-60 kg N/ha as a topdressing by 4 WE. Weed counts in the plots that received 30 kg N/ha as a topdressing were significantly lower than those in the plots topdressed with 60 kg N/ha (see table).

Weed counts and weights before the third weeding (8 WE) and at harvest were not affected by the different rates of nitrogen applied either basally or as a topdressing. The total number and weight of weeds sampled throughout crop growth were likewise not affected.

Weed counts and weights at 2 WE

and weed counts at 5 WE were further analyzed for trend comparisons. Linear responses were significant. At 2 WE, the parameters increased with the amount of nitrogen applied basally while at 5 WE, weed counts increased with the amount of nitrogen applied as a topdressing.

The yield from the plots that received no basal nitrogen was significantly higher than that from the plots that received 20 or 40 kg N/ha as a basal application. Thus, delay in application of fertilizer nitrogen until the first weeding resulted in a reduction in the initial weed growth and an increase in grain yield. ■

Number and weight of weeds^a at 2 and 5 weeks after crop emergence (WE) and rice yield as affected by rate and time of nitrogen application.

Basal	N application rate (kg/ha)			Weeds at 2 WE		Weeds at 5 WE		Rice yield (t/ha)
	Topdressing			No.	Wt (g/m ²)	No.	Wt (g/m ²)	
	2 WE	4 WE	8 WE					
0	30	30	40	115 a	20.0 b	193 a	112.0 a	3.3 a
10	0	50	40	126 a	38.8 b	164 ab	16.2 a	3.2 ab
20	0	40	40	165 a	57.6 ab	163 ab	88.0 a	2.6 b
30	0	30	40	167 a	67.6 ab	98 bc	85.2 a	2.8 ab
40	0	20	40	205 a	76.8 a	76 c	61.6 a	2.6 b

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Weed control in dry-seeded rainfed banded rice and its residual effect on weed growth of the subsequent transplanted rice

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One of the most important rainfed cropping patterns in Bangladesh is dry-seeded rice followed by transplanted rice. Hand weeding is the only means for controlling weeds in dry-seeded rice, but it is becoming expensive. Therefore, butachlor [N-(butoxymethyl)-2-chloro-2',6'-diethylacetanilide] was tested as an alternate means for controlling weeds in dry-seeded rice. Butachlor's residual effect on the weeds of the following transplanted rice was also determined.

Three treatments (see table) with three replications were put in a randomized complete block design. The land

Effect of weed control treatments on performance and weed weight of the first dry-seeded rainfed banded rice and residual effect on the number and weight of weeds of the subsequent transplanted rice crop. BRRI, 1980 aus-t. aman season.^a

Treatment ^b	Dry-seeded rice (BR6) aus 1980				Transplanted rice ^c (Nizersail) t. aman, 1980	
	Stand count (no./0.25 m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./0.25 m ²)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²) at harvest	Weed counts (no./0.25 m ²)	Weed wt (g/0.25 m ²)
	2 WE				4 WT	4 WT
Unweeded check	45.00 a	1.38 a	77.83 a	34.40 a	60.11 a	4.59 a
Butachlor 2.0 kg/ha, fb HW at 3 WE	25.33 b	1.28 a	67.37 a	10.48 b	13.61 a	4.43 a
Hand weeding 2, 5, and 8 WE	43.61 a	2.29 b	103.50 b	3.28 c	43.61 a	6.10 a

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level. ^b fb = followed by. HW = hand weeding. WE = weeks after crop emergence. ^c WT = weeks after transplanting.

used had medium elevation, clay loam with 2.0% organic matter, and pH of 6.8. It was banded and accumulated at least 2 to 3 cm water to allow rice cultivation. After land preparation, seeds of BR6 were sown in rows 25 cm apart at the rate of 100 kg/ha. In the appropriate plots butachlor was sprayed before the germinating rain came. Fertilizers were applied at 80—60-40 kg N, P₂O₅, and K₂O per hectare. Land prepa-

ration for the second crop of transplanted rice was done plot by plot; no treatment was applied to this crop.

Rice stand count, panicle count, weed count, and weed weights were determined by taking random samples from two 0.5- × 0.5-m quadrats in each plot. Grain yields were determined by taking crop-cuts from 3 × 2 m of each plot.

At 2.0 kg/ha, butachlor gave excellent weed control. There were no weeds

in the butachlor-treated plots until 15 days after crop emergence. However, there was a significant reduction (42.9%, see table) in the stand count of BR6 rice. The cultivar seemed to be very much susceptible to butachlor. The yields of the butachlor-treated plots were significantly lower than those of

the plots hand weeded three times.

Weed counts and weights taken at 4 weeks after transplanting of the second rice crop showed no significant difference among the treatments. That indicates that butachlor had no residual effect on the weed growth of the second crop.

Major weeds in both rice crops were *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Cyperus iria* L., and *Fimbristylis littoralis* Gaud.

Further study of butachlor at different rates of application and on different cultivars of dry-seeded rice seems essential. ■

Studies on the chemical control of weeds in dry-seeded wetland rice

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The effectiveness of certain herbicides was assessed in a field experiment during samba (Aug-Dec) with the rice variety ADT31. The test herbicides were propanil, butachlor, and 2,4-D. The herbicides were sprayed once 10 days after sowing. The first weeding was done 30 days after sowing and the second weeding, 45 days after sowing. Each time the monocot and dicot weeds were sorted separately, and their weights recorded by plot. The consolidated wet weights of monocot and dicot weeds were analyzed statistically. The grain

and straw yield of rice also were recorded.

The treatment differences with regard to control of both monocot and dicot weeds were statistically significant. Among the herbicides tested 2,4-D and propanil were superior in controlling monocot weeds; propanil and butachlor were effective in controlling dicot weeds

(see table). The treatment differences with respect to grain yield were also statistically significant. Butachlor and propanil were equally significantly superior to 2,4-D and the hand-weeded check. Butachlor and propanil increased yield by 17.9 and 15.7%, respectively, over the control; 2,4-D increased it by 6.4% over the hand-weeded check. ■

Effectiveness of certain herbicides in the control of weeds for dry-seeded wetland rice.

Herbicide	Rate (kg ai/ ha)	Mean wt (g/m ²)		Grain yield (t/ha)	Percent increase over control
		Monocot	Dicot		
2,4-D	5 kg in 250 liters water	114.60	221.45	2.78	6.40
Propanil	7.5 liters in 250 liters water	155.75	124.95	3.02	15.79
Butachlor	5 liters in 250 liters water	249.20	143.00	3.08	17.90
Control (hand weeding)		323.50	366.50	2.61	-
SE		41.34	48.97	.103	
CD		42.78	150.88	.317	

Light requirements for growth of some perennial paddy weeds

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Knowing the light requirements of weeds is important in determining weed damage to crops and in developing methods of ecological control. We examined the growth response of four major perennial paddy weeds in Japan — *Sagittaria pygmaea*, *S. trifolia*, *Cyperus serotinus*, and *Eleocharis kuroguwai* — to reduced light (60, 45, 22, and 9% relative sunlight) in the field. The plant number and dry weight of shoots of *S. pygmaea* per unit area greatly increased in 60% and 45% sunlight (see figure). The dry weight of shoots of *S. trifolia* also increased in 60% sunlight. But the number of plants and shoot dry weight

Effect of limitation of sunlight on the growth of some perennial paddy weeds, Japan. *70.0 g/m, **369.2 g/m², ***462.5 g/m², ****430.0 g/m². Mean solar radiation at control during the treatment period: 367.3 cal/cm² per day.

of *C. serotinus* and *E. kuroguwai* rapidly decreased with diminishing sunlight. Tuber formation of these weeds (except *S. trifolia*) decreased in such conditions.

The results suggest that the shoot growth of *S. pygmaea* and *S. trifolia* is more adapted to reduced light than that of the two sedges *C. serotinus* and *E. kuroguwai*. ■

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